

Lung Cancer Screening Program Quality Indicators—Review and Recommendations: An International Association for the Study of Lung Cancer Delphi Process Study

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Received 9 July 2024; revised 19 January 2025; accepted 21 January 2025

Available online - 24 January 2025

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Lung cancer screening (LCS) using low-dose-computed tomography reduces lung cancer mortality in high-risk individuals. Evaluating and monitoring LCS programs are important to ensure and improve quality, efficiency, and participant outcomes. There is no agreement on LCS quality indicators (QIs).

Methods: Twenty multidisciplinary members of the International Association for the Study of Lung Cancer used a Delphi process to develop consensus QIs. They considered

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Cite this article as: Tammemägi MC, Borondy-Kitts A, Field JK, et al. Lung cancer screening program quality indicators—review and recommendations: an International Association for the Study of Lung Cancer Delphi process study. *J Thorac Oncol.* 2025;20:871-883.

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ISSN: 1556-0864

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtho.2025.01.019>

50 QIs during information/discussion sessions and two anonymous voting rounds. In total, 80% or more voting agree or strongly agree on a five-point Likert scale determined consensus.

Results: Twenty essential and six desirable QIs were identified in 10 of 11 LCS pathway domain categories (*ENTRY*: Proportion eligible who got screened; *SMOKING_CESSATION*: Proportion of current-smoking individuals offered cessation interventions; *IMAGING*: Proportion screened requiring clinical diagnostic assessment, scan results distribution, proportion scans requiring early follow-up, proportion baseline or regular scans with actionable additional findings; *ADHERENCE* to: Annual or regular scans, early interim scans, clinical diagnostic assessment; *DIAGNOSTIC*: Proportion suspicious-for-lung-cancer scans receiving clinical investigation, undergoing invasive diagnostic procedures; *OUTCOMES*: Cancer detection rate, stage distribution, interval cancer rate; *HARMS*: Number and proportion of serious complications after invasive procedures, non-lung cancer diagnoses after invasive procedures or surgery, 30-day mortality after invasive procedure; *TREATMENT*: Proportion early-stage cancers receiving treatment with curative intent; *WAIT_TIMES*: Suspicious-for-lung-cancer scan to definitive diagnosis, to curative-intent treatment for individuals with early-stage disease, scan completion to reporting results to primary care provider and participant; *EQUITY*: Race, sex, and socioeconomic differences in adherence to regular screens, early-stage cancer treatment, offer of smoking cessation interventions, clinical investigation of suspicious-for-lung-cancer screens).

Conclusions: A review among panel members provided recommended LCS QIs that should be considered in the development of LCS initiatives.

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Keywords: Lung cancer screening; Quality indicators; Quality metrics; Performance indicators; Performance metrics

Introduction

Lung cancer is a major global public health problem and the leading cause of cancer deaths worldwide, with an estimated 2.5 million new cases and 1.8 million deaths in 2022.¹ Low-dose computed tomography (LDCT) lung cancer screening (LCS) has been shown to reduce lung cancer mortality by 20%³ or more in high-risk individuals.^{2,3} On the basis of this evidence, LCS has been recommended for high-risk individuals in the United States by the U.S. Preventive Services Task Force since 2013 and the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid

Services^{4,5} since 2015. There are currently over 4000 sites offering screening in the United States.⁶ In addition, LDCT LCS implementation studies and clinical programs have started up around the world. The Lung Cancer Policy Network's Interactive Map of Lung Cancer Screening as of April 28, 2024, reported 209 LCS clinical trials, implementation studies, and regional or national programs exist in 39 countries.⁶

Monitoring, evaluation, and refinement of LCS programs are important to ensure effectiveness and efficiency. Although several organizations have made recommendations regarding the development of LDCT LCS programs, few have provided comprehensive, systematic approaches to program quality indicators (QIs). A QI is defined as a characteristic or property that is associated with, or that is thought to be, causally associated with, successful program processes and outcomes and reflects the current state of evidence and knowledge in clinical and public health practice. Currently, there are no global QIs for LCS programs. Existing LCS program QIs are inconsistent across countries, vary across guidelines and programs, and may or may not be closely followed within institutions.^{7,8} Selby et al.⁸ reviewed performance metrics for cancer screening and concluded that substantially more guideline performance metrics exist for breast and colorectal cancer screening than for lung cancer. A WHO and International Agency for Research on Cancer consensus concluded that an essential criterion for considering a cancer screening program to be "organized" was that it "should be evaluated with appropriate indicators."⁹

The aim of our study is to develop a set of relevant, measurable, and implementable QIs that can be applied universally to promote and improve the quality of LCS programs. To achieve this, we applied a Delphi process to produce consensus-accepted recommendations among a multidisciplinary, multinational Expert Panel derived from the International Association for the Study of Lung Cancer (IASLC) Early Detection and Screening Working Group (ED&SWG).

Materials and Methods

A modified Delphi method¹⁰ was used to identify essential and desirable QIs from a list of potential QIs on the basis of a literature review using a process similar to that used by the WHO-International Agency for Research on Cancer to determine what constitutes an "organized" cancer screening program.⁹ To decide whether a QI is essential or desirable the expert panelists were instructed to consider the following two properties as described by Zhang et al.⁹: (1) Property 1: an indicator that is important to collect to assess and monitor the quality performance of the screening program or to

identify potential to improve participants' health, reduce harms or increase equity; and (2) Property 2: an indicator that is realistic to collect and analyze and is actionable.⁹ An essential indicator should meet both properties, whereas a desirable indicator meets property 1 but does not completely or easily satisfy property 2.

To guide the selection of QIs with good coverage over the entire LCS pathway, a map was prepared (Fig. 1). Components of LCS programs were a priori placed into domain categories of workflow in sequence ranging from recruitment (Entry) to imaging (Imaging), follow-up (Adherence), diagnostic investigation (Diagnostics), and treatment (Treatment). Some QIs span several pathway categories. For example, Outcomes, Harms, Wait_times, Equity, and Satisfaction QIs are relevant throughout the screening pathway. The Smoking_cessation category is placed in a separate category because smoking interventions may occur in separate programs run independently of the LCS program with referrals from the LCS program, and may occur at more than one time point in the screening pathway. The downstream and overall success of LCS programs depend on upstream successes, with overall program-level successes dependent on QIs in categories along the LCS pathway. Understanding performances of upstream QIs may help explain and identify root causes and corrective actions of poorly performing downstream and overall program QIs.

An outline of methodological and process steps taken in the current study design is presented in the flowchart in Figure 2. The study consists of two sections: information processing and the Delphi consensus study.

Information Processing consists of information gathering, reviewing, interpreting, synthesizing, summarizing,

and reporting. Literature searches were conducted using PubMed, Science Direct, and Google Scholar and took place between April 1 and May 30, 2023, and were limited to English language materials.

Search terms included lung cancer screening program, quality, or performance combined with indicator(s) or metric(s). Word searches within selected articles and reports were conducted for the words indicator and metric. Retrieved articles and report titles, abstracts, and texts were reviewed by authors MCT and ABK for relevance to the current study. Discussion with experts included input from IASLC ED&SWG Expert Panel members. Performance metrics from guidelines for other screened cancers⁸ were reviewed to identify QIs possibly applicable to LCS.

We used a comprehensive approach including metrics from participant and public health perspectives but excluded administrative and economic perspectives. In addition to lists of QIs, a table was prepared of published QI values from the National Lung Screening Trial, the Dutch-Belgian lung-cancer screening trial (Nederlands-Leuven Longkanker Screenings Onderzoek (NELSON) Trial, United Kingdom LCS Programs, Ontario Health (Cancer Care Ontario) lung screening pilot, American College of Radiology (ACR) Lung Cancer Screening Registry (LCSR), and Lahey Hospital and Medical Center (Lahey) LCS Program to provide examples of QI values from current LCS trials, pilot, registry, and programs. The following were not included as part of this study: (1) supporting evidence for the effectiveness of LCS. These have been described elsewhere and are established^{2,3}; (2) implementation guidelines for the development of LCS programs. Such guidelines have been published^{11,12}; (3) radiological imaging quality assurance methods.

Figure 1. Lung cancer screening pathway domain categories.

Figure 2. International Association for the Study of Lung Cancer Early Detection and Screening Working Group Delphi study flowchart.

These are highly technical and specialized. Detailed quality assurance methods for screen imaging are described elsewhere^{13,14}; (4) indicators related to cost

effectiveness, budgetary impact, or financial analyses; and (5) indicators of treatment details and responses to treatments, including survival analyses.

We did not include specific LCS program QI threshold values for acceptable performance, as single appropriate universal values do not exist. Different jurisdictions and institutions need to establish standards on the basis of what is appropriate for their populations, settings, and resources. We provide published selected LCS QI values from several sources as examples of existing values.

Delphi Consensus Study

Details of the Delphi process steps and chronology are presented in [Figure 2](#). Potential QI under consideration came from literature review and Expert Panel suggestions. All polling was conducted electronically using Microsoft Excel spreadsheets to collect survey responses, and discussion meetings were conducted virtually over Zoom.

Statistical Methods

In reviewing the literature, proportions, and confidence intervals for descriptive epidemiologic measures were calculated using the binomial exact method. Poll #1 and #2 voting by the Expert Panel took place using a five-point Likert scale (strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and strongly agree), on whether the QI is considered essential, desirable, or neither. For Delphi QI voting, the proportion of agree or strongly agree was calculated among all responding Expert Panel members and a priori consensus was achieved when the proportion of agree or strongly agree was 80% or higher.³ In addition, the mean Likert score for each item was calculated. When the item response in Voting Poll #1 had a proportion of agree or strongly agree of less than 80% but the mean Likert score for the item was 4.0 or higher, the QI was included in the voting for Poll #2 for essential or desirable classification. This allowed Expert Panel members to reconsider initial votes after evaluating results of Poll #1. The proportions and mean scores for each survey item after Poll #1 were provided to Expert Panel members before voting for Poll #2. Microsoft Excel and Stata/MP version 18.0 software (Stata LLP, College Station, TX) were used for analyses.

Results

Information Processing

Of the more than 4000 article titles reviewed, 153 potentially relevant abstracts were identified leading to 82 full article reviews. A total of 47 articles were relevant, seven of which were used as final inputs for the list of potential LCS program QI candidates for Delphi Poll #1. Sources of guideline and report information on LCS program QIs for the current study and sources of QIs values are presented in [Table 1](#).^{2,3,7,13,15-33} Similar QIs

from multiple sources were included only once in the list of QIs for polling consideration. The location of each guideline and report QI in the LCS pathway categories is presented in [Table 2](#).^{1,7,11,13,15-19} Commentaries regarding specific QIs in the [Table 1](#)^{2,3,7,13,15-33} guidelines and reports are presented in [Supplementary Appendixes 1 to 7](#).

QIs from guidelines/reports, literature review, and Expert Panel recommendations were developed into a final Delphi Poll QI voting list of 50 candidate QIs ([Supplementary Table 1](#); Selected LCS program QI values from trials, pilots, registry, and programs are presented in [Supplementary Spreadsheet 1](#)).^{2,3,20,24,25,27-33}

Delphi Process and Consensus Quality Indicators

Twenty of the 21 IASLC ED&SWG members volunteered to serve on the Expert Panel. The panelists had diverse academic and clinical backgrounds, experiences, and expertise and were from 13 countries ([Table 3](#)).

Expert Panel member participation rates in both Polls #1 and #2 were 95% (19/20). Voting in Poll #1 resulted in consensus on 12 QIs rated as essential ([Table 4](#) and [Supplementary Table 1](#)). Ten indicators did not achieve 80% consensus votes but had average Likert scores of 4 or higher (out of 5) indicating high approval. Expert Panel members revoted on these 10 Poll #1 “near misses” in Poll #2 to determine if they were essential or desirable. Eight were voted as essential in Poll #2.

Voting in Poll #1 found 20 indicators that were not close to consensus on being essential. In Poll #2, the Expert Panel voted to determine whether any of these QIs were desirable. Expert Panel members also suggested nine new QIs, which were considered in Poll #2 for either essential or desirable status. Post-Poll #2 Discussion led to minor alterations ([Supplementary Text S2](#)).

After Polls #1 and #2 and post-poll discussions, the Expert Panel determined 20 QIs to be essential, six desirable, and 24 neither (total = 50) ([Table 4](#) and [Supplementary Table 1](#)). One or more essential QIs were identified in 10 of 11 LCS pathway categories. Only Satisfaction had no essential or desirable QIs.

Discussion

Overview

Our study identified LCS QIs that cover a wide range of the LCS pathway. Many of the selected upstream QIs have causal connections with downstream indicators. Corrective interventions in upstream deficiencies are expected to lead to improvements in downstream indicators and overall program indicators.

One QI in the Entry category was considered essential—“Of eligible individuals, what proportion

Table 1. Sources of Lung Cancer Screening Program Quality Indicators and Selected Quality Indicators Values

Guideline and Report Sources of Lung Cancer Screening Program Quality Indicators	Supplementary Appendix ^a
1 Screening for Lung Cancer-CHEST Guideline and Expert Panel Report (2021) ¹⁵	1
2 NLCRT Proposed Quality Metrics for Lung Cancer Screening Programs (2021) ⁷	2
3 ACR Lung Cancer Registry (2021) ¹³	3
4 CPAC (2017) ¹⁶⁻¹⁸	4
5 CPAC (2023) ¹⁶⁻¹⁸	5
6 Cancer Australia ¹⁹	6
7 Developing a Pan-European Technical Standard for a Comprehensive High-quality Lung Cancer CT Screening Program. An ERS Technical Standard (2023)	7
Sources of lung cancer screening program quality indicator values	
8 NLST ²	
9 Dutch-Belgium NELSON Trial ³	
10 United Kingdom lung cancer screening performance by analysis of baseline data from five “programmes” ²⁰ (two trials [UKLS ²¹ and LSUT ²²], one observational cohort study [Nottingham Lung Health MOT ²³], two “NHS commissioned screening services”, one pilot [Manchester Lung Health Check pilot ^{24,25}], and one project [Liverpool Health Lung Project ²⁶]). Aggregate data from five UK lung cancer screening programmes are included in the analysis.	
11 Manchester Lung Health Check Pilot ^{24,25,27} (Although the Manchester Lung Health Check Pilot is included in the pooled study number 3, it contains additional indicator values not provided in number 3, so is provided separately also.)	
12 Ontario Health (Cancer Care Ontario) lung cancer screening Pilot ²⁸	
13 American College of Radiology Lung Cancer Screening Registry ²⁹	
14 Lahey Hospital and Medical Center LCS program ³⁰⁻³³	

^aSupplementary Appendix 1 to 7 provides listings of QIs from each guideline and report, with commentary.

ACR, American College of Radiology; CPAC, Canadian Partnership Against Cancer; ETS, European Thoracic Society; LCS, lung cancer screening; LSUT, Lung Screen Uptake Trial; MOT, UK Ministry of Transportation (vehicle safety and environmental standards test); NELSON, Nederlands-Leuven Longkanker Screenings Onderzoek; NHS, National Health Services; NLCRT, National Lung Cancer Roundtable Project; NLST, National Lung Screening Trial; QI, quality indicator; UK, United Kingdom; UKLS, United Kingdom Lung Cancer Screening Trial.

received a scan?” This QI directly measures the extent to which individuals who could benefit from screening get screened ($\text{Probability}_{(\text{Screened} | \text{Eligible})}$). The Expert Panel did not evaluate eligibility criteria as these are chosen by individual jurisdictions as part of LCS program development.

Smoking cessation interventions and programs are an important and effective component of LCS programs.^{34,35} Smoking cessation improves both outcomes and cost-effectiveness of LCS.^{36,37} Tracking smoking indicators can help monitor cessation programs and possibly improve cessation program interventions. The expert panel considered it more important to monitor the offering of smoking cessation services to current smoking participants than to monitor successful cessation achievement. Successful long term smoking cessation usually takes multiple attempts,³⁸ and using smoking cessation rates as the QI may underestimate the long-term impact of cessation interventions.

The Imaging category is well represented with consensus-derived QIs (three essential and one desirable), covering suspicious LDCT LCS examinations and actionable additional findings. Monitoring Imaging QIs can help inform if program changes are needed and

provide a sense of the health care system LCS program burden.

Adherence category QIs include the proportion of participants adherent to follow-up recommendations in their computed tomography lung scan radiology report, specifically for regular annual or biennial screening, early interim imaging, or diagnostic assessment for screens that are highly suggestive of lung cancer. The time analysis window for assessing appropriate adherence to follow-up may vary with jurisdictions and across countries. Adherence is important to track, as good lung cancer outcomes and LCS program cost-effectiveness are based on returning for screening or diagnostic evaluation at appropriate time intervals.

The proportion of individuals with lung cancer screens that are highly suggestive of lung cancer (e.g., Lung-RADS 4B and 4X) who are referred to and attend a diagnostic clinical investigation is an important QI as there is a high proportion of these individuals who have lung cancer and cannot benefit from screening if they do not attend the clinical assessment.

An important QI in the Diagnostics category is the proportion of participants undergoing an invasive procedure for diagnostic purposes. Some guidelines and

Table 2. Lung Cancer Screening Pathway Categories for Guideline and Report Quality Indicators and IASLC Quality Indicators (Blue Font)

Category	Smoke_											Number	Number
Guideline/Report	Entry	Cessation	Imaging	Adherence	Diagnostics	Outcomes	Harms	Treatment	Wait_Time	Equity	Satisfaction	Indicators	Categories
CHEST 2021 LCS ^{15,a}	1	4	2		2, 3	3, 5	3	5				5 domains	7
NLCRT ^a 2021 Survey 2 final consensus (initial) ^b	1 (1)	2 (3)		3 (9), 4 (10), 5 (11)					6 (15)			6	4
NLCRT ^a 2021 ⁷ Survey 1 initial ^c	2, 4		6, 7			8, 14	5, 12, 13					9 others	3 others
ACR January 2023 ¹³	2	3	3 ^d	1		10 CDR, 7 PPV						26	5
CPAC 2017 ¹⁶			1		2	6, 7, 10, 3	4, 8, 5	9				10	5
CPAC 2023 ^{17,18}	1	3	4	2	5	6, 7, 8, 10 ^e			9	Strata		10	8
Cancer Australia ¹⁹	2		5, 6, 8, 9 ^f	3, 4 ^g	10	13, 14, 16, 17, 18	7 ^h 12	15	4 ^g , 9 ^f , 11		1	18	9
ERS (2023) ¹¹	1-4	5-7	8-11	22	12	14, 16, 21	13, 15, 18, 19	15, 17, 20				22	8
IASLC 2024 QIs (essential/ desirable)	1	2	3-5/21	6-8	9-10	11-13	14-15/ 22-23	16	17/24-25	18-20 / 26	0/0	26	10

^a2021 *Screening for Lung Cancer CHEST Guideline and Expert Panel Report*¹ provides general topics or categories to be considered, not specific quality indicators that can be measured.

^bNumbers in parentheses indicate the original indicator number assigned in the original reporting document.

^cExcluded from final consensus indicators.

^d20 radiology quality assurance metrics are excluded.

^e10 is interval cancer rate per number screened. It is defined in a way that makes it less useful - See text and [Supplementary Appendix S4](#) for discussion.

^fShows up in two categories.

^g“Timely scan rate,” can reflect both participant adherence and program process issues (e.g., delays due to capacity issues).

^hIncorrectly reported to be on the topic of “Predictive value.”

ACR, American College of Radiology; CDR, cancer detection rate; CPAC, Canadian Partnership Against Cancer; ERS, European Respiratory Society; IASLC, International Association for the Study of Lung Cancer; NLCRT, National Lung Cancer Round Table; PPV, positive predictive value; QI, quality indicator.

Table 3. Characteristics of the Expert Panel Members

Panelist	Country	Gender	Degrees	Specialty
1	Australia	Female	M.B.B.S.	Pulmonary Medicine
2	Brazil	Male	MD	Thoracic Surgery
3	Canada	Male	PhD	Epidemiology
4	Canada	Male	MD	Pulmonary Medicine
5	People's Republic of China	Male	MD	Pulmonary Medicine
6	People's Republic of China	Male	MD, PhD	Thoracic Surgery
7	Colombia	Female	MD	Pulmonary Medicine
8	Germany	Male	MD, PhD	Pulmonary Medicine
9	Hungary	Female	MD, PhD	Radiology
10	India	Female	MD, PhD	Pulmonary Medicine
11	Italy and United Kingdom	Male	MD	Thoracic Surgery
12	Serbia	Female	PhD	Molecular Oncology
13	South Africa	Male	MD, PhD	Pulmonary Medicine
14	United Kingdom	Male	MD, PhD	Pulmonary Medicine
15	United Kingdom	Male	PhD	Basic Science
16	United States	Female	MS, MPH	Patient Advocate
17	United States	Female	MD, PhD	Radiology
18	United States	Female	MD, MS	Diagnostic Radiology
19	United States	Male	MD	Diagnostic Radiology
20	United States	Male	MD, PhD	Pulmonary Medicine

reports separate this QI by type of procedure, for example, image-guided needle biopsy, surgical biopsy, or surgical resection. Some interpret this QI as a measure of harm done, but this is incorrect, as invasive procedures are essential for establishing a diagnosis that is necessary for treatment.

Outcomes QIs reflect performance in multiple categories along the screening pathway. QIs related to cancer detection rate, stage distribution of lung cancers diagnosed, and interval cancers were considered essential. These QIs reflect the efficiency of the screening program and good performance in these QIs is expected to translate into meaningful lung cancer mortality reductions. Regarding stage distribution, the appropriate QI is a demonstration of a relatively lower advanced cancer incidence, which has been shown in lung cancer to have a 92% correlation with a reduction in lung cancer mortality in trials.³⁹ Early-stage incidence or proportions are poor metrics to use as overdiagnosis can lead to an overestimate of screening effectiveness.

QIs describing the histologic distribution of lung cancers, sensitivity or false-negative rate, and specificity or false-positive rate were not selected as essential or desirable. It is surprising that these were not selected as they are routinely provided in LCS articles and reports. Sensitivity and specificity are foundational measures of test accuracy, so their exclusion may be inappropriate. Nevertheless, the interval cancer rate, which represents one minus sensitivity, was selected as an essential Outcome QI.

Although positive predictive value often influences health policy decision-making, it is strongly influenced

by the prevalence of disease and thus values may not be comparable across sites and over time. In addition, formulas used to calculate positive predictive value have differed between studies.

Mortality was listed as an indicator in two reports. It is a difficult metric to track as it requires large sample sizes, long follow-ups, and linkages to external databases to identify deaths and causes of death, and it is not a feasible QI in many programs. (See [Supplementary Text 1](#) for a discussion of using incidence and mortality as an LCS QI.)

One QI in the potential Harms category is the proportion of participants who underwent an invasive procedure for benign disease or non-lung cancer malignancy. It is important to appreciate that it is a clinical necessity to determine whether a suspicious finding is cancer or not, and this often requires obtaining a tissue sample by invasive methods. If the biopsy comes back benign, it is good news for the participant. It is poor clinical practice not to thoroughly assess a suspicious-for-lung-cancer screening result. Although minimizing the number of invasive procedures for non-lung cancer disease may seem beneficial from some perspectives, from a clinical perspective undue avoidance of invasive procedures can lead to missed lung cancer diagnoses, leading to greater harm. The rate of biopsies for non-lung cancers may vary owing to geographic differences in endemic fungal infections and tuberculosis.

Monitoring participant receipt of excess radiation dose is an important potential Harm QI because cumulative exposure over long periods of screening can lead to radiation-induced cancers. The ACR LCSR suggests

Table 4. Final IASLC Delphi Study Consensus Essential^a and Desirable^a Lung Cancer Screening Program Quality Indicators by Pathway Category

Category = ENTRY

1. Proportion of risk-assessed, eligible individuals offered screening who enter the lung cancer screening (LCS) program and receive a scan during a defined period.

Category = SMOKE_CESSATION

2. Proportion of current smoking participants who were offered smoking cessation counseling or intervention.

Category = IMAGING

3. Proportion of individuals with scans requiring clinical diagnostic assessment for suspicion of lung cancer.

4. Distribution of scan results stratified by findings, for example, by LungRADS scores, volume/volume doubling time or negative, indeterminate, positive. (The labels and categories depend on the radiologist scan interpretation and result management system used.)

5. Proportion of individuals with screens requiring any test or clinical assessment related to lung cancer other than the next regular scan (e.g., annual or biennial scan).

21. Proportion of individuals with baseline or annual scans with actionable additional findings (other than suggestive of lung cancer). (Each institution will use their own preferred definition of actionable additional finding.)

Category = ADHERENCE

6. Proportion of individuals returning for annual (or biennial) scans within a reasonable time window of the date of the next recommended scan after a previous negative scan result.

7. Proportion of individuals returning for early interim imaging within a reasonable time window, e.g., following Lung-RADS 3, 4A, or volumetric indeterminate finding.

8. Proportion of individuals with screens that are suggestive of lung cancer (e.g., Lung-RADS 4B, 4X, or on the basis of volume/volume doubling time) who are referred to and attend diagnostic assessment. This indicator excludes individuals with “probably benign” or “indeterminate” results that require interim scans before their next regularly scheduled scans.

Category = DIAGNOSTICS

9. Proportion of individuals with abnormal scans that are suggestive of lung cancer (e.g., Lung-RADS 4B or 4X, or on the basis of volume/volume doubling time) that receive a clinical investigation, which includes determination of next steps.

10. Proportion of participants with abnormal scans that underwent an invasive diagnostic procedure.

Category = OUTCOMES (Screening program outcomes)

11. Cancer detection rate.

12. Stage distribution of lung cancers.

13. Proportion of all lung cancers occurring in the screened cohort that are interval lung cancers (detected after a negative screen).

Category = HARMS (POSSIBLE)

14. Number and proportion of potentially serious complications occurring after invasive procedures. (Potentially serious complications can be defined by the institution.)

15. Number and proportion of screened individuals who have an invasive procedure for what turns out to be non-lung cancer, for example, for a benign nodule.

22. Number and proportion of screened individuals who have lung surgery for what turns out to be non-lung cancer, for example, for a benign nodule.

23. 30-day mortality after invasive procedures.

Category = TREATMENT

16. Proportion of participants with early-stage screen-detected lung cancer who underwent treatment with curative intent. (Measures receipt of appropriate treatment.)

Category = WAIT_TIMES, Include wait times from

17. Suggestive of lung cancer scan result to definitive clinical diagnosis (either lung cancer or not lung cancer).

24. Suggestive of lung cancer scan result to referral for treatment with curative intent (e.g., surgery or SBRT) for individuals with early-stage lung cancer.

25. Scan completion to reporting of results to the primary care provider and participant.

Category = EQUITY [LCS pathway category is in square brackets]

Proportions of the following quality indicators that differ by participant characteristics: race-ethnicity, sex-gender, or SES. Possible SES measures include the highest education level attained, rural-urban residence, deprivation indices, and area-based census-derived estimators of SES, such as median household income.

NOTE: A comprehensive evaluation of disparities might evaluate inequities in many of the essential and desirable quality indicators. Nevertheless, such an exhaustive evaluation in many settings may be unrealistic. We polled a limited selection of quality indicators below to develop a sense of priorities.

18. Proportion of individuals who return for their regular annual or biennial scan after a normal previous scan. [Adherence]

19. In individuals with screen-detected early-stage lung cancer, the proportion receiving treatment with curative intent. [Treatment]

20. Proportion of current smoking participants who were offered smoking cessation counseling/intervention. [Smoke_cessation]

26. Proportion of individuals with abnormal scans that are suggestive of lung cancer that receive a clinical investigation, which includes determination of next steps. [Diagnostics]

Category = SATISFACTION

None

A desirable indicator may have property 1 but not completely or easily satisfy property 2.

^aAn essential indicator should have both of the following properties. 1The indicator is important to collect to assess and monitor the quality performance of the screening program or to identify the potential to improve participants' health, reduce harm, or increase equity. 2The indicator should be realistic to collect and analyze and be actionable.

IASLC, International Association for the Study of Lung Cancer; LCS, lung cancer screening; QI, quality indicator; SBRT, Stereotactic Body Radiation Therapy; SES, socioeconomic status.

measures of radiation exposures that are stratified by BMI.¹³ To date, neither the frequency of receipt of excess radiation in LCS practices according to ACR LCSR radiation exposure measures nor the impact of such information on LCS practices, have been reported. Once further evidence on LCS excess radiation is established, this indicator should be re-assessed for inclusion as a QI.

The treatment QIs focus on assessing if participants with early-stage screen-detected lung cancer receive appropriate treatment. For a screening program to be successful in reducing lung cancer mortality, successful treatment of early-stage (stage I and II) disease must be provided. Generally, treatment regimens that follow the diagnosis of screen-detected lung cancers lie outside the imaging and diagnostic departments and are outside the scope of screening programs. Nevertheless, because the success of a screening program hinges on the receiving appropriate treatment of early-stage disease, we selected one relevant summary metric in this category.

Candidate wait time QIs reflecting successful LCS processes were proposed at multiple places along the LCS pathway. Selected as an essential QI was wait time from suspicious-for-lung-cancer screening results to definitive lung cancer diagnoses, because timely diagnosis and treatment are crucial to getting the best outcomes for participants with lung cancer.

Equity QIs such as disparities by race-ethnicity, sex-gender, and socioeconomic status have been associated with unequal health outcomes and can exist at multiple points along the LCS pathway.^{40,41} To date, *Equity* QIs have not been included in most LCS QI guidelines. Nevertheless, this is an important LCS program QI category and should be considered for routine inclusion. Our study found three essential and one desirable Equity QIs. These are existing metrics in the Smoking cessation, Adherence, Diagnostics and Treatment categories stratified by race-ethnicity, sex-gender, and socioeconomic status.

Satisfaction QIs such as high participant satisfaction may not be essential for LCS programs to lead to substantial lung cancer mortality reductions. It was not selected as a QI. Nevertheless, patient satisfaction has potential to be a QI as it may lead to higher adherence, which in turn should lead to better LCS clinical outcomes.

QIs derived from the Delphi process are considered to have good face validity.⁴² In the current study, QI values from multiple sources were collected ([Supplementary Spreadsheet 1](#)) to provide a sense of achievability and the distributions in their absolute values. For several indicators, remarkable QI value consistency exists between groups. For example, distributions of screening results by Lung-RADS scores were similar in baseline and post-baseline strata. For other QIs, differences exist between groups, but this is expected owing to differences in LCS programs and participant characteristics.

Fit With Past Studies

The IASLC LCS QIs generally agree with the collective thinking in the [Table 1](#)^{2,3,7,13,15-33} guidelines and reports. In the IASLC QIs which do not match those in the guidelines and reports, the IASLC QIs are filling in gaps. None of the IASLC LCS QIs are inconsistent or conflicting with other guideline and report QIs.

Limitations and Strengths

We may have missed some important QIs, such as the false-positive proportion. Misreporting of the false discovery rate as the false-positive rate initially after the publication of the National Lung Screening Trial results led to widespread misunderstanding and loss of support for LDCT LCS. Reporting of correct values for modern LCS programs is expected to be reassuring to potential participants and the medical community. It is surprising that sensitivity and specificity were not found to be QIs as they are foundational measures of test accuracies. Achieving consensus in this Delphi study required passing a relatively high threshold ($\geq 80\%$ voting agree or strongly agree). For these indicators, outlier extreme negative votes by a few individuals pulled the mean score away from consensus. This occurrence reflects a limitation of the Delphi process. The recommended LCS QI list could have been different if the definition of consensus and analysis plan had varied. Failure to achieve consensus should not be interpreted to mean that a QI is not important in all settings.

The relatively long list of IASLC LCS QIs may seem to present a heavy data capture burden, but it has been reported in real-world settings, such as the ACR LCSR, the Ontario Pilot, and the Lahey LCS program, that extensive LCS QI collection is possible ([Supplementary Spreadsheet 1](#)).^{28,43}

Our study does have strengths. The Delphi process is a more structured method for evaluating hard-to-test study questions, compared with unstructured, non-quantitative discussion groups. The Expert Panel was large, and international and contained individuals with multiple and diverse expertise. In contrast to many previous guidelines and reports with limited numbers of QIs, our study identified an extensive list of LCS QIs, covering all but one LCS pathway domain category.

Clinical and Public Health Implications

The IASLC QIs are not intended to be a rigid, firm, obligatory list, but rather a choice of QIs covering a range over the LCS pathway that institutions and jurisdictions can select from and modify or adapt to individual settings and needs. The IASLC LCS

QIs are ready for immediate application and are expected to be useful for existing and developing LCS programs.

Future Directions

QIs are not static and need upgrading over time. Some QIs may need to be developed that are institution or jurisdiction-specific and can augment the IASLC QIs. In the future, collecting and compiling values for QIs in a registry database will allow comparison of LCS program performances across institutions and jurisdictions and the development of recommended QI ranges for different populations.

Conclusion

The information review and IASLC Delphi process produced consensus-derived essential and desirable LCS program QIs that covered most of the domain categories in the LCS pathway. Application of the selected QIs is expected to help guide evaluation, monitoring, and improving LCS initiatives and programs.

CRedit Authorship Contribution Statement

Martin C. Tammemägi: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing.

Andrea Borondy-Kitts: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Program administration, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing.

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Disclosure

Dr. Tammemägi reports consulting fees from Nucleix, and Medial EarlySign. Travel support from International Association for the Study of Lung Cancer (IASLC) to present Quality Indicator study results at the WCLC 2024 in San Diego. Travel support from the Rescue Lung Society to present Quality Indicator results at the Rescue Lung Society Conference 2024 in Boston. Ms. Kitts is a Rescue Lung Society Board member and a Lung Cancer Policy Network Steering Committee member. Dr. Henschke, serves on the advisory board of Lunglife AI without compensation; is a named inventor on a number of patents and patent applications relating to the evaluation of pulmonary nodules on CT scans of the chest which are owned by Cornell Research Foundation (CRF). Since 2009; does not accept any financial benefit from these patents including royalties and any other proceeds related to the patents or patent applications owned by CRF; and is the President and serves on the board of the Early Diagnosis and Treatment Research Foundation. She receives no compensation from the Foundation. The Foundation is established to provide grants for projects, conferences, and public databases for research on early diagnosis and treatment of diseases. Recipients include I-ELCAP, among others. The funding comes from a variety of sources including philanthropic donations, grants, and contracts with agencies (federal and non-federal), imaging, and pharmaceutical companies relating to image processing assessments. The various sources of funding exclude any funding from tobacco companies or tobacco-related sources. Dr. Kerpel-Fronius reports honorarium from Boehringer Ingelheim Speaking bureau and Merck Sharp & Dohme, support for travel costs Roche and Ewopharma, Hungarian Society of Radiologists President-elect and Hungarian Society of Pulmonologists (member of the board). Dr. Koegelenberg, AstraZeneca, reports honoraria for lectures GlaxoSmithKline Honoraria

for lectures. Dr. Zulueta reports holding positions on Median Technologies Advisory Board, Heart Lung Technologies Advisory Board, Oncoswab Co-founder, honoraria Median Technologies Webinar on AI in lung cancer screening, stock & stock options Heart Lung technologies Minor percentage of options for a role in Advisory Board Oncoswab Minority percentage as co-founder. Dr. Santos reports honoraria from Canon Medical, Johnson & Johnson, and andon, The Bristol Myers Squibb Foundation, leadership role in ProAr Foundation, receipt of equipment, materials, drugs, medical writing, gifts, or other service from Johnson & Johnson. Dr. Rzyman reports honorarium from AstraZeneca; and positions on the advisory boards of AstraZeneca, Medtronic, Merck Sharp & Dohme, and Bristol-Myers Squibb. Dr. Yankelevitz, is a named inventor on a number of patents and patent applications related to the evaluation of chest diseases including measurements of chest nodules; has received financial compensation for the licensing of these patents; is a named inventor on a number of patents and patent applications related to the evaluation of chest diseases including measurements of chest nodules; and has received financial compensation for the licensing of these patents, HeartLung Advisory board and owns equity in HeartLung Median Technology, Carestream and Lunglife AI Medical advisory board of Median Technology, Carestream, and Lunglife AI, Accumetra Consultant and co-owner of Accumetra HeartLung Advisory board and owns equity in HeartLung. Dr. Lam is an expert advisor of the Canadian Partnership Against Cancer Payments made to me, IASLC Partial support for attending the World Conference on Lung Cancer, Nuclix Inc. Medical Advisory Board unpaid, Steering Committee, International Cancer Screening Network Unpaid. Dr. Huber participated in advisory boards for Janssen Germany, Merck Germany, Boehringer Ingelheim, Sanofi Germany, and Novocure Germany, deputy chair of the Early detection and screening committee of IASLC, co-chair of the ERS/ESTS task force fitness for therapy of lung cancer. The remaining authors declare no conflict of interest.

Supplementary Data

Note: To access the supplementary material accompanying this article, visit the online version of the *Journal of Thoracic Oncology* at www.jto.org and at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtho.2025.01.019>.

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